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Adoption of Itax Technology and its Impact on Tax Filing by Users in Kenya

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Abstract

Technology is revolutionizing the way industries operate. Tax administration bodies in most countries are incorporating technology in their day to day operations because ICT helps to develop every facet of tax administration, be it, tax collection, tax audit, taxpayer services, or any other tax process. Though the iTax system of tax filing was introduced in Kenya by the KRA in 2014 to enable the taxpayers to file and submit their taxes online, its application and adoption amongst the taxpayers has been very minimal therefore the study sought to assess significance of adoption of iTax technology and its impact on tax filing by users in Kenya basing on the local and international studies published between 2011 to 2022. The study revealed that countries all over the world have shifted from the manual and traditional tax filing system to the electronic tax system; tax administration bodies are embracing technology for effective and efficient management of tax collection, tax audit and taxpayer services; most taxpayers prefer to seek help from tax consultants or tax agencies during tax registration, assessment and filing; taxpayers' intention to individually use tax e-filing system can be boosted if the taxpayers are technologically ready and finally, basic computer knowledge influences an individual's intention to use social networking programs. The study recommended that the existing iTax filing architecture should be redesigned by the tax department to ensure comfort of use to the tax payers. Secondly, it was recommended that the government of Kenya should put in place a system that ensures accessibility to technological infrastructure so as to give the taxpayers motivation to adopt the use of iTax technology without necessarily paying agents to file tax on their behalf.

KeyWords: Tax payer perception, adoption of iTax technology, impact on tax filing by user

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology is revolutionizing the way industries operate. Every aspect of administration as well as administration bodies are shifting to information and communication Technology (ICT) for more effective and efficient management of their respective tasks. Tax administration bodies are also following this trend because ICT helps to develop every facet of tax administration, be it, tax collection, tax audit, taxpayer services, or any other tax process. Murigu (2017) asserted that tax bodies for example the Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA) plays a critical role in revenue administration. These revenue authorities ensures that the citizens or taxpayers and all parties affected by the tax regime comprehend their obligations and responsibilities as outlined in the tax policies of a given tax regime. Tax payers as well play an important role in ensuring that they meet their tax obligations since they are in the best position to declare their tax information under the law (Ndoti, 2020).

The main aim of a revenue authority is to ensure that collection of all duties and taxes are done according to the tax laws and that the confidence in the tax system and its administration is not prejudiced (KRA, 2015). Taxpayer's actions play a critical role in ensuring compliance with the law. Where the tax payer is ignorant, careless, and reckless or decides to deliberately evade tax as well as tax administration weaknesses, instances of failure to comply with the law is unavoidable (Mutheu, Mwangi & Njenga, 2019). Tax administration should therefore put in place structures and strategies that lead to minimum non-compliance with tax law. Electronic tax systems are swiftly replacing paper-based tax recording systems. Mutheu et al. (2019) further put forward that with these systems, tax administration bodies are hopeful that tax returns and submission will be made stress-free. According to the Centre for Tax Policy and Administration (2004), taxpayers are able to submit their tax returns through the internet directly from their premises and the returns can be reflected in the revenue authority platform, with the introduction of electronic filing system. This method of submission is intended to enable the tax payers to file their tax returns in a faster, convenient and in a way that will lead to minimal cost as well as ensuring a smooth, efficient and reliable process of tax returns both by the tax administration bodies and taxpayer, (Centre for Tax Policy and Administration, 2004).

The *iTax* system was introduced in Kenya by the KRA in 2014 so as to enable the taxpayers to file and submit their taxes online. The fully incorporated and computerized *iTax* is a web grounded system presented to simplify the tax processes, increase revenue collection and reduce the time taken to submit tax returns, (Elmi, 2021). The application of *iTax* and its adoption amongst the taxpayers in Kenya has been very minimal (Murigu, 2017). It is evident that many tax payers opt to seek for the tax filling and submission services at the Huduma Centers or KRA offices every financial year so as to comply and meet with the deadlines as prescribed in the Kenyan tax laws. The long queues at the services provision points is no shock that *iTax* adoption has faced many setbacks. The limited adoption may be attributed to a number of challenges that taxpayers face individually as well as behavioral issues relating to adopting of new technologies (Elmi, 2021).

It can be argued that because individual character influences the use of technology, organizations should be conscious of the relationship that exists between character and use of technology during information systems initiation process. This means that institutions should align their strategy so as to ensure an increase in technology approval on the basis of personalities of the user. Personality types can have negative or positive effects respectively, on the adoption and use of information technologies in any organization, (Erdo & Esen, 2011)

Costa et al. (2017), found out that a strong relationship exists between computer related attitudes and computer use in entrepreneurial ventures since attitude influences the acceptance of an entrepreneur to use a particular technology, and also impacts on whether an entrepreneur will integrate ICT into his or her business ventures. The study reveals that the attitudes of entrepreneurs in relation to technology greatly affect their readiness to adopt and integrate computers into their businesses. Therefore, to incorporate and implement technology into entrepreneurial orientation successfully, the attitude of the entrepreneurs matter a lot. With positive attitude, they can easily offer useful insight on adoption and integration of ICT into the business world.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

KRA developed *iTax*, an online tax platform to enable integration of registration process, tax preparation and returns, tax filing and tax payment by every individual liable to tax in Kenya (KRA, 2015). The online tax filing system is gaining importance as it allows the public to carry out their tax responsibility for the development of

the country. However, it is evident that the uptake and personal responsibility of the taxpayers to individually use the system in Kenya has been very little as evidenced by the long queues at Huduma centers and cyber cafes towards the end of every financial year seeking assistance from the agencies to file tax returns on their behalf (Murigu, 2017). Previous studies on tax and e-filing have concentrated on the impact of online tax filing on tax compliance as well as analysis of taxpayer's intention to use e-filing tax system.

Despite studies by different researchers (Kimea, Chimilila, & Sichone, (2019); Elmi, (2021); Mutheu et al., (2019), on the *iTax* adoption determinants and intention to use the e-filing system, little has been done on significance of the current study variables and impact on tax filing by users in Kenya. Adoption of *iTax* technology comprises of components relating to; perception of the taxpayer on the use of *iTax* system, self-efficacy of the tax payer as well as access to technological infrastructure by the taxpayer during tax filing period (Elmi, 2021). This research seeks to establish significance of adoption of *iTax* technology and impact on tax filing by users in Kenya. The paper will be important for the government and the Kenya Revenue Authority in examining the relationship between accessibility of technological infrastructure, perception and self-efficacy of tax payers on adoption of the electronic filing system - *iTax*. Moreover the paper will inform taxpayers about the recent trends in technology and how they can make themselves ready to use and adopt the *iTax* platform for easy, comfortable and efficient tax return processing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

The study was anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which was advanced in order to study individual acceptance of technology. Defined by Davis (1985), it has two beliefs: perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. These two determine the user's attitude towards adopting new technologies. TAM has explicitly been developed in view of describing and explaining technology adoption and use. The TAM theorizes that using technology is mainly determined by the individual's belief in its perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived ease of use influences the behavioural intention to use the technology that then determines the actual adoption and use of technology.

TAM can validly predict personal intention of an individual to use and self-report on the usage of a given technology. It has proven to be a theoretical model in helping to explain and predict user behavior of information technology. The TAM framework is also one of the most widely used theoretical framework in explaining individuals' acceptance behavior towards an information system such as tax e-filing. TAM is a good theoretical tool to understand why technology is adopted and traces how external variables influence belief, risk, attitude, and intention to use (Chuttur, 2017).

TAM is also preferred and is adopted in this paper because it suits the paper's scenario of explaining individual's acceptance to use the *iTax* system. Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use predict attitudes, which in turn influence intention to use a technology and this intention consequently impacts on the actual use. In the TAM model, people who perceive technology as useful and easy to use will accept it more readily than those who do not, hence the use of TAM model in this paper.

2.2 Empirical Review

Taxpayer Perception and Impact on Adoption of iTax Technology by users in Kenya

Tahar, Riyadh, Sofyani and Purnomo (2020) conducted a research on the role of technology readiness in Indonesia. The main objectives of the study was to establish the relationship between taxpayers intention in terms of perceived usefulness, attitude, perceived ease of use, information quality, perceived credibility of the system as well as information system quality. Primary data was collected from the national armed forces and state police in Semarang City whereby 150 questionnaires were distributed, processed and analyzed. Hypotheses were tested by using the multiple linear regression and path analysis. The results indicated that perceived ease-of-use and perceived security had a positive effect on the use of e-filing, while perceived usefulness has no effect on the use of e-Filing. The study found out that there is a significant relationship between technology acceptance model determinants and taxpayers intention to use the system.

Octavia, Widyahayu, & Muhamad (2021), conducted a study on the effects of attitude towards e-tax systems, adoption of e-tax systems, isomorphic forces and trust in tax authority to tax compliance. The study aimed to investigate whether taxpayer attitude towards an electronic filing system, adoption of the e- filing system and trust in the government tax authority would affect an individual tax payer's behavior to voluntarily exhibit tax compliance attitude. The study also examined whether adoption of e-tax filing systems could increase obligatory tax compliance. The study sample comprised of 152 SMEs taxpayer registered in Pratama Medan Petisah. IBM SPSS Statistics version 25 was used to process the data and multiple regression tests were conducted to analyze the data. The study results indicated that taxpayer's attitude in relation to electronic filing system, adoption of the e- filing system and trust in the government tax authority significantly affects voluntary tax compliance positively. The findings also revealed that the uptake of e-filing system had positive significant influence on enforced tax compliance.

Tazilah (2017) researched on the determinants of taxpayers intention towards manual tax system, in Klang Valley of Malaysia. Adoption of e-filing in the area was below the expectation despite over seven year's implementation. In order to pay the taxes every year, there were citizens who preferred to continue to submit their annual income tax by filing up the hard copy form instead of using e-filing system. According to study, the issues identified in adoption of electronic filing system were the user discomfort about e-filing technology, perceived insecurity of e-filing, lack of internet self-efficacy and skills. The study revealed that normally people who are over 40 years old did not prefer to use the technology matters and the fact that people who paid the tax every year are from that majority. Besides that, it was found out that most of the people just used e-government service website to check their summonses instead of fully utilizing the online and that this happened due to a lack of Malaysia community to the exposure of technology usage. It was recommended that the Malaysian government should focus on improving the acceptance of the e-filing system among its taxpayers since it increases tax collection.

Kimea, Chimilila and Sichone (2019) carried out a study in Tanzania on analysis of taxpayers' intention to use e-filing system in Tanzania, controlling for self-selection. The paper aimed at analyzing the factors affecting the intention of the taxpayer's to use electronic tax platform. The paper employed TAM framework and used econometric tests to observe self-selection endogeneity bias in taxpayer's intention to use the system. The study results through endogenous switching model showed that risk, performance expectancy and social influence have significant effects on the intention to use the e-filing system. The research also found out that these factors

affect users and non-users intentions in different ways hence a differentiated strategy. From the findings, it can be inferred that the way this factors affect the different age set is different.

Mutheu et al. (2019), studied on attitudinal and technological determinants of *iTax* system acceptance in Kenya. The study was based on the technology acceptance model. The objective of the study was to determine the factors influencing acceptance of *iTax* system. The paper examined and presented variables including taxpayer's attitude towards technology and the *iTax* system. The paper employed a descriptive study and targeted taxpayers in the eastern part of Nairobi city in Kenya. The study revealed a positive technology suitability regarding technological determinants of *iTax* acceptance. The study concluded that suitability, security and coverage of the *iTax* platform and taxpayer's positive attitude towards *iTax* greatly influence the Studies carried out locally include those of picked as representative, to be the focus of the study. In addition ten tax consultants were also interviewed. A descriptive survey design was used and a stratified sampling technique was used to create a sampling frame ensuring that different and diverse types of entities were included in the survey. Data was collected using self-administered questionnaires and an interview guide. The collected data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Scientist software and findings presented using tables. The findings of the study revealed that the more useful individuals perceive their chosen filing method, the more likely they are to use that method to file.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

4. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study involves a review of qualitative literature related to the adoption of e-filing systems, specifically focusing on Kenyan taxpayers. The study collected data from articles published between 2011 and 2021, sourced from platforms like books, SSRN, Google Scholar, and the Emerald database. Relevant studies were chosen based on keywords related to topics like tax papers' perception of e-filing and the role of technology readiness. The study relies on two theoretical frameworks: the technological acceptance model and the economic theory. It examines the impact of adopting *iTax* technology on tax filing, considering three independent variables: taxpayers' perception, self-efficacy, and accessibility to technological infrastructure.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study's key findings highlight a global trend where tax administration bodies are increasingly embracing technology to improve the efficiency of tax collection, audits, and taxpayer services. This shift from traditional manual tax filing to electronic systems requires taxpayers to register with tax authorities and manage their

individual tax accounts. The introduction of e-filing systems places the responsibility for tax assessment and filing on taxpayers themselves, aiming to simplify the process, boost revenue collection, and reduce the time needed to submit tax returns. However, the study reveals that in many African countries, taxpayers have not fully embraced these e-filing systems and often rely on assistance from tax consultants or agencies. To encourage individual use of e-filing, the study suggests that taxpayers' readiness to adopt the use of technology plays a crucial role, and this adoption can be enhanced through training, logistical support during registration, and ensuring strong internet connectivity.

Additionally, the research indicates that the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is widely employed in studies conducted in Africa and beyond to support the integration of technology into electronic tax filing. The TAM examines individual technology acceptance by considering factors like perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, which influence users' attitudes toward adopting new technologies. The study also finds that readiness to adopt e-filing is influenced by factors such as the ease of use, perceived usefulness, the availability of technological infrastructure, and users' self-efficacy. Embracing all the components of the iTax system is shown to have a positive impact on various aspects of tax administration and taxpayer compliance. The findings further suggest that individuals with basic computer knowledge and previous computer experience tend to exhibit a greater inclination to use social networking programs. The study recommends redesigning existing e-tax filing architecture and implementing user-friendly systems to motivate taxpayers to continue using the system in the future.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The assessment of significance of adoption of iTax filing system and its impact in tax filing by users in Kenya is in essence an attempt to ascertain whether readiness of the taxpayer to adopt the use iTax filing system plays a role in the individual uptake of the technology. Through theoretical and empirical literature, this study concludes that the taxpayer's intention to use and attitude towards a given technology greatly affects the level of acceptance and use of the technology.

When empirically appraised, it emerges that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, accessibility to internet connectivity and a taxpayer's beliefs or the extent to which one is capable to establish and perform the particular courses of action so as to attain a given purpose, are the major influences of technological readiness. These, as outlined can be used as a roadmap in shaping and making taxpayers to adopt the iTax system and relate with the platform on an individual basis.

Finally, the following suggestions for further study are grounded on the limitations recognized in existing literature. First, it is critical to conduct empirical studies to assess the role of access to technological infrastructure on adoption of iTax filling system. This is especially the case because there is scanty literature on infrastructure availability and its role in adoption on e- tax filling. Another possible area of interest would be the assessment of the emerging models of technological inclusion. This is with respect to analysing the influence of externalities such as environmental and social affects in the ever changing technological regime.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the current research offer several recommendations to the top management within organizations to enforce higher diffusion of e-filing technologies through determining the factors that influence e-filing. There is also the need for policy interventions by the government and other financial stakeholders to facilitate financing for tax payers that need to equip their businesses with the necessary IT infrastructure.

Government need to ensure that there is reliable technical infrastructure, ensuring that users' views and situation are taken into consideration in project implementation and having strong project and monitoring system in place. It is imperative for governments to think about social inclusiveness in the context of infrastructure while making decisions about technology and development.

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